

Stefano Bagnulo

Armagh Observatory and Planetarium, UK

Polarimetric calibration and accuracy:
lessons learnt from present instrumentation

with contributions from:

A. Cikota (ESO) - L. Fossati (Graz) - J.D. Landstreet (UWO) - F. Patat
(ESO) - F. Snik (Leiden University) - M. Sterzik (ESO) - A. Stinson (AOP)

FORS @ ESO VLT

ISIS @ ING WHT

NARVAL@TBL & ESPADONS @ CHFT
(HIGH RESOLUTION SPECTROPOLARIMETRY)

HARPSpol @ 3.6m

- 1) Imaging + Spectropolarimetry
- 2) Polarimetric capabilities in the continuum
- 3) Widely and wildly used
- 4) Data archive

- Surface structure of asteroids, TNOs, and other flying rocks (imaging linear polarimetry and spectropolarimetry)
- Dust of comets (Imaging linear polarimetry and spectropolarimetry)
- Stellar magnetic fields (circular spectropolarimetry)
- Supernovae (Imaging linear polarimetry and spectropolarimetry)
- Interstellar medium
- AGN
- Characterisation of the atmospheres of exoplanets (so far just a wishful thinking with FORS)

<http://background.uchicago.edu/~whu/intermediate/polarization/polar1.html>

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$$P_L = [(Q/I)^2 + (U/I)^2]^{1/2}$$

$$Q/I = P_L \cos(2\theta)$$

$$\theta = 1/2 \arctan(U/Q) + \theta_0$$

$$U/I = P_L \sin(2\theta)$$

$I+Q$

$I-Q$

$$\frac{\text{TOP}-\text{BOTTOM}}{\text{TOP}+\text{BOTTOM}} = \frac{I+Q-(I-Q)}{I+Q+(I-Q)} = \frac{Q}{I}$$

$$\frac{\text{TOP}+\text{BOTTOM}}{\text{TOP}-\text{BOTTOM}} = \frac{I+Q+(I-Q)}{I+Q-(I-Q)} = \frac{I}{Q}$$

$I+Q$ +

$I-Q$ +

$I+Q$ +

$I-Q$ +

$$\frac{\text{TOP-BOTTOM}}{\text{TOP+BOTTOM}} = \frac{Q}{I} + f(\text{trash can}, \text{trash can})$$

$$\alpha = 0^\circ$$

$$\alpha = 45^\circ$$

$$\alpha = 0^\circ$$

$$\alpha = 45^\circ$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left[\frac{1+Q - (1-Q)}{1+Q + (1-Q)} + \text{trash} \right] - \left[\frac{(1-Q) - (1+Q)}{1-Q + (1+Q)} + \text{trash} \right] \right\} = \frac{Q}{1}$$

I+Q

I-Q

$$\left(\frac{f^{\parallel} - f^{\perp}}{f^{\parallel} + f^{\perp}} \right)$$

$$P_V = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{f^{\parallel} - f^{\perp}}{f^{\parallel} + f^{\perp}} \right)_{-45^{\circ}} - \left(\frac{f^{\parallel} - f^{\perp}}{f^{\parallel} + f^{\perp}} \right)_{+45^{\circ}} \right]$$

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2.4.3 Instrument Flexures

The image motion due to instrument flexure under gravity is less than 0.2 un-binned pixels over a 1 hour exposure with the standard and a 2 hour exposure with the high resolution collimator for zenith distances less than 60° . Arcs and flats are however taken at daytime and at the zenith. This will introduce an offset between night time calibration based on telluric emission lines and day time calibrations based on arc lines depending on the zenith distance and the absolute angle of the Cassegrain rotator. The passive flexure compensation of the FORS instruments, based on support struts on the camera section was optimized down to the following small but not negligible image motions between zenith and the given zenith distances:

Figure 2.4: Results of flexure measurements as a function of the rotator position for the SR collimator at zenith distance of 40° . The panels show the flexure in *un-binned* pixels across (X) and along (Y) the slit. The solid green circle represents zero-flexure.

Are polarimetric properties
constant in the field of view?

30.4%

31.8%

9.9%

11.1%

-3.0%

3.0%

-0.3%

0.3%

-0.3%

0.3%

$$\begin{aligned} P'_Q &= \cos(2\chi) P_Q + \sin(2\chi) P_U \\ P'_U &= -\sin(2\chi) P_Q + \cos(2\chi) P_U \\ P'_V &= P_V . \end{aligned}$$

χ is the instrument position angle on sky

INSTRUMENT PA ON SKY (DEG)

Instrumental polarisation

$$P_Q^{\text{instr}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(P_Q^{(0)} - P_Q^{(90)} \right)$$

$$P_U^{\text{instr}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(P_U^{(0)} - P_U^{(90)} \right).$$

Siebenmorgen et al. 2014

HD149404 2015-05-12

During the upgrade:

- PMOS → PMXU?
- Attention to flexures (metrology?)
- Attention to cosmic rays
- Allow imaging templates in polarimetric OBs
- Fully characterise the transparency of the polarimetric optics and monitor instrumental polarisation in a more sophisticated way
- Further investigate cross-talk
- Further investigate polarimetric optics in the field of view
- Allow sky flats while wave plate is rotating
- Try to reduce overheads

Thank you!